

Supplementary Material

Supplementary Table 1. Primers for gene expression analysis by RT-qPCR

Target	No. GenBank	Direction	Sequence (5'→ 3')
GAPDH	NM_001289745.2	<i>Forward</i> <i>Reverse</i>	CACATGGCCTCCAAGGAGTAAG CCAGCAGTGAGGGTCTCTCT
HPRT	NM_002046.6	<i>Forward</i> <i>Reverse</i>	ACCCACGAAGTGTGGATA AAGCAGATGGCCACAGAACT
TNF-α	NM_000594.3	<i>Forward</i> <i>Reverse</i>	TCCTTCAGACACCCTCAACC AGGCCCCAGTTTGAATTCTT
IL-1β	NM_000576.2	<i>Forward</i> <i>Reverse</i>	GGGCCTCAAGGAAAAGAATC TTCTGCTTGAGAGGTGCTGA
IL-6	NM_000600.4	<i>Forward</i> <i>Reverse</i>	TACCCCCAGGAGAAGATTCC TTTTCTGCCAGTGCCTCTTT
IL-10	NM_000572.2	<i>Forward</i> <i>Reverse</i>	GCCTAACATGCTTCGAGATC TGATGTCTGGGTCTTGGTTC
IL-4	NM_000589.3	<i>Forward</i> <i>Reverse</i>	GCCACCATGAGAAGGACACT ACTCTGGTTGGCTTCCTTCA
TLR4	NM_138554.4	<i>Forward</i> <i>Reverse</i>	TGAGCAGTCGTGCTGGTATC CAGGGCTTTTCTGAGTCGTC